

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF MULCHES ON FLOWERING AND FRUIT ATTRIBUTES OF CUSTARD APPLE CV. DHARUR -6

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MS Received: 10.11.2024; MS Revised:21.12.2024; MS Accepted:22.12.2024

MS 3321

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE)

Abstract

The present investigation entitled "Different types of mulches on off season bearing of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) cv. Dharur 6" was conducted on well-established custard apple orchard of six year old at Custard Apple Research Station, Ambajogai, during 2022-23. The experiment was carried out in Randomized block design with seven treatments replicated thrice. The treatment were as (T1) wheat straw, (T2) Dried grass, (T3) soyabean straw, (T4) sugarcane bagasse, (T5) Dhaincha, (T6) Black coated plastic sheet and (T7) Control. The results revealed that, there were significant variations in flowering and fruit attributes of custard apple due to mulching. Number of flowers per plant ranged from 145.86 to 163.46. Maximum number of flowers per plant was recorded in treatment black coated plastic sheet (T6, 163.46). Maximum fruit set (43.78%), fruits per plant (71.57), fruit weight (204.71 g), fruit length (7.4 cm), fruit volume (188.1 cm³) and fruit diameter (9.56cm) was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet T₆. From this experiment it can be concluded that the T6 (Black coated plastic sheet) was most effective with respect to Flowering, fruit attributes.

Keywords: Custard Apple, mulching and Mulches).

Introduction

Custard apple (*Annona squamosa*) is a member of family annonaceae, having chromosome number is 2n=14. It is one of the delicious fruit due to present of pleasant flavour, mild aroma and sweet test have a universal acceptance. Custard apple is also known by different name such as sweet soap, Sitaphal, sharifa, and 'attichaka' in various growing regions. In india mainly grown in Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Assam, Maharashtra, Odisha, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu. In Maharashtra it is commonly grown in Solapur, Aurangabad, Beed, Pune, Buldhana, Dhule, Nagpur, Aurangabad and Akola Districts. In Marathwada region it is mainly grown in Beed, Ambajogai, Latur, Daulatabad and Aurangabad. Custard apple is grown in tropical climate, having semi deciduous in nature. Flowers are greenish yellow in colour have six petals and two whorls, numerous stamens and carpel.

It requires high humidity which is necessary during flowering to improve fruit set. It requires 60-80cm annual rainfall for better growth and development. It requires summer temperature from 15 to 25⁰ C. It can not stand frost and or a cold for long period. Soil should be sandy loam having pH neutral to slightly acidic. Hand

pollination is practiced in custard apple to enhance the fruit set. Due to high temperature, low atmospheric humidity, lack of irrigation water and natural stresses results in less number of flowers, poor fruit setting and low yield and degraded quality of fruit too (pande and kamboj 2005). The nutritive value of custard apple is very high. It contains Magnesium, which helps in protecting heart against diseases as well as relaxing muscles. It has many alkaloids, such as nicocodine, sqamorine, aporphine, romerine, squamonine, corydine, norisocoroydine, glaucine and anononaine in different parts of the plants. Custard apple seeds has insecticidal and abortifacient properties.

Materials and Method

The present study "Different types of mulches on off season bearing of Custard Apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)" was conducted during the year 2022-23. The details of the materials used, method adopted and statistical analysis followed during the course of this investigations are described below. The experiment was carried out at instructional-cum-research field of Custard apple Research Station, Ambajogai, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidhyapeeth Parbhani, during the year 2022-23.

Table 3.1 Details of the Experiment

1	Name of the crop	Custard apple (<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.)
2	Family	Annonaceae
3	Variety	Dharur-6
4	Experimental Design	Randomized Block Design
5	Number of treatments	7
6	Spacing	5 × 5 m
7	Number of replications	Three (03)
8	Number plant / treatment	Three (03)
9	Total Number of plant	63
10	Number of mulches	Six (06)

Table 3.2 Details of the treatment:

Treatment No.	Treatment details	Thickness (cm)
T1	Wheat straw	5-7cm
T2	Dried grass	5-7cm
T3	Soybean straw	5-7cm
T4	Sugarcane bagasse	5-7 cm
T5	Dhaincha	5-7 cm
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	(100μ)
T7	Control (without mulch)	-

The experiment was carried out on well-established Custard apple Cv. (Dharur6) orchard with the tree spacing of 5×5 m at Custard apple Research station, Ambajogai during 2022-23. The experiment consists of 07 treatment with 3 replications in Randomized Block Design (RBD). with 3 plant per treatment. Mulching materials was laid out in the field with 3 plant per treatment in summer season. The statistical analysis was completed by standard statistical method suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1995).

Result and Discussion

The field experiment entitled “Studies on Different types of mulches on off season bearing of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.)” was carried out at instructional-cum-research field of Custard apple Research Station, Ambajogai, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani during the year 2022-23. The data has been statistically analyzed by using randomized block design. The results obtained are presented under suitable headings and subheadings.

Effects of types of mulches on number of flowers per plants

Significant variations were observed among all the treatments for
Table 1 Effect of types of mulches on number of flowers per plant

Treatment	Treatment details	Number of flowers perplant
T1	Wheat straw	150.4
T2	Dried grass	151.1
T3	Soybean straw	154.1
T4	Sugarcane baggase	156.0
T5	Dhaincha	158.4
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	163.4
T7	Control	145.8
	S. E. ±	0.60
	C. D. at 5%	1.85

Fruit Set (%)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for fruit set per cent (Table 2). Fruit set ranged between 38.24 to 43.78 %. Maximum fruit set was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 43.78 %) followed by treatments Wheat straw (T1, 42.44 %) Dried grass (T2, 40.44 %) and Soybean straw (T4, 39.82 %). Minimum fruit set was recorded in treatment Control (T7, 38.24 %). Different mulches like black polyethylene mulch, soybean straw mulch and other mulch significantly increased the fruit set and reduced fruit drop in custard apple as compared to other treatments

Table-2 Effects of types of mulches on fruit set (%)

Treatment	Treatment details	Fruit set (%)
T1	Wheat straw	42.44
T2	Dried grass	40.44
T3	Soybean straw	39.82
T4	Sugarcane baggase	39.10
T5	Dhaincha	38.36
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	43.78
T7	Control	38.24
	S. E. ±	0.56
	C. D. at 5%	1.75

Number of fruits per plant

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for Number of fruits per plant (Table 3). Number of fruits per plant ranged from 55.8 to 71.57. Maximum number of fruits per plant was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 71.57) followed by the treatment Wheat straw (T1, 63.83) and Soybean straw (T4, 61.23). Minimum number of fruits per plant was recorded in Control (T7, 55.80).

The successful mulching in black coated plastic paper flower plant Wang *et al.* (2015) observed maximum fruits per plant in peach with black polyethylene mulch followed by straw mulch and minimum

Table. 3 Effect of types of mulches on number of fruit per plant

number of flowers per plant (Table 1). Number of flowers per plant ranged from 145.86 to 163.46. Maximum number of flowers per plant was recorded in treatment black coated plastic sheet (T6, 163.46) followed by dhaincha (T5, 158.00) and sugarcane baggase (T4, 156.00) and minimum number of flowers per plant was recorded in treatment control (T7, 145.86). The mulching with flower plants, there was suppression of weed growth and increased microbial activity in the soil. It also enhanced the activity of nutrient availability in the soil which improved flowering.

Also mulching increased pollination by the insect pollinators in custard apple which resulted increase in fruit setting in custard apple. This effect may be due to better efficiency to control weeds more moisture retention which in turn increased the flower retention. Availability of essential nutrients promoted flowering, fruit set and controlled fruit drop in these plants which ultimately led to higher fruit yield. This is in conformity with the findings of Singh *et al.* (2009) in mango cultivars.

this effect may be due to better efficiency to control weeds more moisture retention which in turn increased the flower retention. Availability of essential nutrients promoted flowering, fruit set and controlled fruit drop in these plants which ultimately led to higher fruit yield. The successful mulching of flower plants in conserve soil moisture in fruit trees there was an increase in population of pollinating insects and also an increase in pollination percentage which can affect positively on fruit set and negatively on fruit drop. The finding results are similar by Lalruatsangi and Hazarika (2018) in acid lime.

with control. This is in conformity with the findings of Singh *et al.* (2009) in mango cultivars.

Bakshi *et al.* (2014) the results revealed that strawberry is very responsive to the different mulching materials. but black polythene mulch gave the best results in terms of reducing weed population (1.00/m²), increasing plant height (21.67 cm), plant spread (31.24 cm), number of leaves per plant (18.33), number of flowers per plant (28.33), number of fruits per plant (12.12), number of achenes/fruit (317.70), fruit weight (11.83 g), fruit length (3.93 cm), fruit breadth (3.00 cm), yield (143.38g/plant), total soluble solids (7.63 OB), total sugars (7.00 %), vitamin-C (57.77 mg/100 g).

Treatment	Treatment details	Number of fruits per plant
T1	Wheat straw	63.83
T2	Dried grass	61.13
T3	Soybean straw	61.23
T4	Sugarcane baggase	61.00
T5	Dhaincha	60.76
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	71.57
T7	Control	55.80
	S. E. ±	0.91
	C. D. at 5%	2.81

Fruit weight (g)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for fruit weight (Table 4). Fruit weight ranged from 155.05 to 204.71 g. Maximum fruit weight was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 204.71 g) which was followed by treatment Wheat straw (T1, 191.91 g) and Dried grass (T2, 191.18 g). Minimum fruit weight was recorded in Control (T7, 155.05 g).

This might to be the effect of black coated plastic paper on conserving soil moisture and weed control. And mulching has been founding Increasing in the the photosynthesis thus increasing fruit

Table 4 Effect of types of mulches on fruit weight (g)

Treatment	Treatment details	Fruit weight (g)
T1	Wheat straw	191.91
T2	Dried grass	191.18
T3	Soybean straw	180.66
T4	Sugarcane baggase	187.44
T5	Dhaincha	185.61
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	204.71
T7	Control	155.05
	S. E. ±	2.20
	C. D. at 5%	6.80

Fruit length (cm)

The data presented revealed that the fruit length was significantly influenced by different types of organic and inorganic mulch treatments. The values of fruit length varied from 5.43 to 7.40 cm under different treatments. The maximum fruit length (7.40 cm) was recorded in the fruit trees black coated plastic sheet (T6, 7.40cm) followed by treatment dried grass (T2, 7.06 cm) and Wheat straw (T1, 6.75 cm) which were at par. minimum fruit length (5.43 cm) was noticed in fruits under control.

This might be due to the effect of black polyethylene mulch on weed control, moisture conservation and more absorption solar energy. Mulching has been found to increase tree canopy which ultimately

Table 5 Effect of types of mulches on fruit length (cm)

Treatment	Treatment details	Fruit length(cm)
T1	Wheat straw	6.75
T2	Dried grass	7.06
T3	Soybean straw	6.56
T4	Sugarcane baggase	6.43
T5	Dhaincha	6.66
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	7.40
T7	Control	5.43
	S. E. ±	0.30
	C. D. at 5%	0.93

Fruit volume (cm³)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for fruit volume (Table 6). Fruit volume ranged from 146.36 to 188.10 cm³. Maximum fruit volume was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 188.10 cm³) followed by treatments Soybean straw (T3, 180.5 cm³) and Dried grass (T2, 176.16 cm³) Minimum Fruit

weight. Similar findings were also recorded by Mathieu and Aure (2000) in apple.

Kaushik Das (2018) Among the different mulching treatments, black polythene showed maximum soil moisture retention with improved soil properties. This treatment also exhibited maximum physico-chemical qualities of fruits followed by paddy straw and paddy husk. Black polythene mulch gave 80% marketable fruits on the 9th day of storage while control showed minimum storage life as evident from CO₂ evolution and total soluble solids content of fruit.

resulted in increase in photosynthesis and thereby increased fruit size, weight and volume. Similar findings were also recorded by Sharma and Khokhar (2006).

Bakshi *et al.* (2014) also recorded the maximum fruit length (3.40cm) and breadth (2.34cm) under black polythene mulch in strawberry. Higher fruit breadth was recorded in plants mulched with black polythene in pomegranate. The organic and inorganic mulching provided consistently improved available soil moisture in plant basin due to which the plant roots remained probably active throughout the irrigation season resulted in optimum availability of nutrient and proper translocation of food materials which accelerate the fruit growth and development.

volume was recorded in treatment Control (T7, 146.36 cm³).

This might be due to the effect of black polyethylene mulch on weed control, moisture conservation and more absorption solar energy. Mulching has been found to increase tree canopy which ultimately resulted in increase in photosynthesis and thereby increased fruit size, weight and volume. Similar findings were also recorded by

Sharma and Khokhar. (2006) .

Fruit weight, fruit size and fruit volume of Strawberry was significantly higher under drip irrigation in combination with plastic mulch as compared to control (Singh *et al.* 2007). Also highest fruit weight

was observed in Nagpur mandarin under black polythene mulch followed by grass mulching, white polythene and paddy straw mulching .

Table 6 Effect of types of mulches on Fruit volume (cm³)

Treatment	Treatment details	Fruit volume(cm ³)
T1	Wheat straw	167.33
T2	Dried grass	176.16
T3	Soybean straw	180.50
T4	Sugarcane baggase	174.70
T5	Dhaincha	173.76
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	188.10
T7	Control	146.36
	S. E. ±	1.29
	C. D. at 5%	4.00

Fruit diameter (cm)

Significant variation was observed among all the treatments for fruit diameter (Table 7). Fruit diameter ranged from 7.43 to 9.56 cm. Maximum fruit diameter was recorded in treatment Black coated plastic sheet (T6, 9.56 cm) followed by treatments Wheat straw (T1, 8.96 cm) and Dried grass (T2, 8.86 cm). which were at par. and Minimum Fruit diameter was recorded in treatment Control (T7, 7.43 cm).

Among the different mulching treatment black polythene mulch shows that highest increase the fruit weight, fruit length, fruit

diameter (Das *et al.* 2016). Effect of various mulching recorded highest fruit length, fruit diameter, fruit volume, fruit weight, fruit juice% were recorded maximum in polythene mulch with black side facing .

The results are in line with the findings of Bhandari *et al.* (2017) who reported that larger fruit size in terms of (length 7.34cm and breadth 7.47) were obtained under black polythene mulch which was due to more plant growth and development under micro-climate condition resulting in better nutrient uptake in pomegranate. Table 7 Effect of types of mulches on Fruit diameter (cm)

Treatment	Treatment details	Fruit diameter (cm)
T1	Wheat straw	8.96
T2	Dried grass	8.86
T3	Soybean straw	7.93
T4	Sugarcane baggase	7.63
T5	Dhaincha	8.73
T6	Black coated plastic sheet	9.56
T7	Control	7.43
	S. E. ±	0.29
	C. D. at 5%	0.91

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